

Bektashi Tarika

also known as “Bektashiyya”, “Bektashi Tariqa”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Greek, Language, Turkic, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Hanafi

The Bektashi tarika, a Sufi religious order, traces its founding to Hacı Bektash Beli, who arrived in Anatolia in the 13th century CE (7th century AH) from Khorasan. The religious order became influential within the Ottoman Empire, in part due to its association with the powerful Janissary corps; Bektashi tekkes, or lodges, were built across the Ottoman Empire, most notably in the Balkans, Anatolia, and the Aegean. Although the order became powerful in the Ottoman Empire, which officially followed the Sunni Hanafi school, the practices of the order include recognition of the twelve imams, a Shi'ite practice. The group's practices also drew from popular mysticism and incorporated some Christian elements, such as the welcoming of new members with wine, bread and cheese, which is perhaps drawn from the Artotyrite version of Christian communion. The order was led by the Celebi, who lived in the *pir-evi* (dervish lodge) built over the tomb of Hacı Bektash near Kirshehir and Kayseri in central Anatolia. Influential Bektashi writings include the *Makalat* of Hacı Bektash, which was written in Arabic and later translated into Turkish. Due to the affiliation of the Janissary corps with the Bektashi tariqa, the destruction of the Janissary corps in 1826 by Mahmud II negatively affected the continuation of the order. As of 1915, Bektashi communities continued to exist in Asia Minor, the Balkans (especially Albania), and the Aegean (see F. W. Hasluck). However, Bektashi tekkes were also built in Cairo, Baghdad, and Karbala. Today, the Bektashi order exists most prominently in Albania. Both men and women took part in Bektashi rites. Bektashi tekkes, or lodges, were most commonly built on the outskirts of densely inhabited areas; this contrasted with tekkes of other Sufi orders that were more commonly built in urban centers (Hasluck, p. 85-86). An example of this phenomenon can be seen clearly in the old city of Rethymno on Crete: while the Veli Pasha Bektashi lodge was built in the agricultural land outside of the city center, two other Sufi lodges were built within the city shortly after the Ottoman conquest of Rethymno.

Date Range: 1240 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Ottoman Empire, European Provinces and Anatolia

Region tags: Crete, Greece, Rethymno, Aegean

The Bektashi order was most common in the Balkans, Anatolia, and the Aegean.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hasluck, F.W. “Geographical Distribution of the Bektashi.” *The Annual of the British School at Athens Sessions 1914-1915; 1915-1916*, no. XXI (1916): 84-124.
- Source 1: Jazexhi, Olsi. “The Bektashi Tarikah of Dervishes,” 2007.

– Source 1: Tschudi, R. "Bektashiyya." In *Encyclopedia of Islam*, I:1161–63. Brill, 1986.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://historicalcrete.ims.forth.gr/Toponyms/listing/tzami-veli-pasa>

– Source 1 Description: Online map and description of a dervish tekke in Rethymno, Greece that was a Bektashi tekke at the time of Evliya Celebi (17th century).

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Bektashi>

– Source 2 Description: Encyclopedia Britannica entry on the Bektashi religious order.

– Source 1 URL: <https://kryegjyshataboterorebektashiane.org/en/the-archives-of-the-world-bektashi-seat/>

– Source 1 Description: Description of Bektashi archives in Tirana, Albania.

– Source 1 URL: http://dlib.statistics.gr/Book/GRESYE_02_0101_00009.pdf

– Source 1 Description: Census of Crete from 1913, used together with Hasluck 1916 (below) to calculate Bektashis as a percentage of the population.

– Source 1 URL: http://dlib.statistics.gr/Book/GRESYE_02_0101_00009.pdf

– Source 1 Description: Census of Crete from 1913, used together with Hasluck 1916 (below) to calculate Bektashis as a percentage of the population.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://kryegjyshataboterorebektashiane.org/en/bektashi-literature-in-albania/>

– Source 1 Description: Description of Bektashi literature written in Albania.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The Ottoman janissary corps was affiliated with the Bektashi tarika.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: While the Islamic faith was hereditary, participation specifically in the Bektashi order was generally not assigned from birth.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, membership in the Bektashi tarika was by choice; however, Janissaries who were chosen through the Devshirme system did not have the same degree of choice in their affiliation with the Bektashi tarika.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Generally, Bektashi tekkes and mosques were endowed by individuals; however, some of these individuals held prominent governmental positions.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

Notes: The Ottoman Empire had complementary legal systems of Islamic law, as practiced by the four Sunni madhabs (with official emphasis on the Hanafi madhab), alongside Kanun, or imperial law.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are physically marked as such (e.g. branding, mutilation):

– No

↳ Apostates are executed:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are publicly executed:

– Yes

↳ Other corporal punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Beating

Notes: One account describes an apostate in the late 1700s being beaten (Deringil 550).

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

- ↳ Punished in the afterlife:
 - Yes

- ↳ Cursed by "high god":
 - No

- ↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):
 - No

- ↳ Other divine punishment:
 - No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 3000

Notes: Hasluck, writing in 1915, described the number of Bektashis in Rethymno as 3,000 before the events of 1897, and 1,000 after 1897.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 4.9

Notes: Hasluck's figure of Bektashis in Rethymno ca. 1897 (3,000) is compared to the overall population of Rethymno province in 1913. (for the official census, see (http://dlib.statistics.gr/Book/GRESYE_02_0101_00009.pdf). This is not an exact comparison; a better estimation could be reached by comparing the Ottoman census pre-1897 to the figure given by Hasluck of the Bektashi adherents in the region.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

- ↳ Are they written:
 - Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: The angel Jibril (Gabriel) is considered responsible for delivering the revelation of the Quran to the Prophet Muhammad.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

Notes: The Quran is considered to be revealed, rather than inspired, by the high god.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Notes: The Prophet Muhammad received the revelation of the Quran from God, but it is not considered to have originated with him.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Mosques

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: tekke

Notes: Bektashi communities usually had a tekke (dervish lodge).

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Calligraphy

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Notes: Pilgrimage to türbes of prominent Bektashi individuals is attested from the Ottoman period.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Belief in the migration of souls is attested (Tschudi p. 1162).

↳ In a human form:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: washing of the corpse prior to interment

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Türbe

Notes: Türbes (mausoleums) are most frequently associated with saints' burials.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Omnipotent

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Knowledge of all living creatures
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- |

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: The supreme high god exhibits anger and sorrow.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside

of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Angels can see humans everywhere.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Angels record good and bad deeds.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Angels are able to record good and bad deeds.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Knowledge of places inaccessible to humans

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: Angels do not possess hunger.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and jinn are the major categories of supernatural beings.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Signals the end of times.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: May either be near or distant future.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: May either be near or distant future.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

Notes: This distinction is most present in the Ottoman legal system: 'custom' is referred to and relied upon, unless it contradicts religious law, in which case religious law (based upon divinely mandated moral commands) takes precedence.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society (excepting slaves, aliens)

Notes: Moral requirements apply to Muslims, but not other religious groups within society, which may have their own moral requirements.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

– Yes

Notes: Some members made a vow of celibacy; the celibates wore earrings as identifiers (Tschudi p. 1162).

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Overall, membership did not require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations; however, circumcision was required for men.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 5

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Number of participants: 50

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Average interval [hours]: 24

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:
– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Notes: Muslim men are required to receive circumcision, but this is not specifically a marker of the Bektashi order.

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Sufi orders within the Ottoman Empire often had distinctive forms of dress; Bektashis wore a white cap with either four folds (signifying the four gates) or twelve folds (signifying the twelve imams) (Tschudi p. 1162).

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: Bektashi celibates wore a single earring to identify themselves (Tschudi 1162).

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tekkes affiliated with other Sufi orders also had imarets (soup kitchens).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: While there was a formal hierarchy within the Bektashi tarika, this did not strictly constitute a bureaucracy.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents interacted with the bureaucracy of the Ottoman state.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Fountains are a common feature of Ottoman mosques, including Bektashi mosques and tekkes.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Taxes were levied by the Ottoman state.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: The janissary corps, which fulfilled many functions analogous to those of a police force, was strongly affiliated with the Bektashi tarika.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Within the Ottoman court system, judges were not only chosen from within the Bektashi tarika.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents were subject to the Ottoman legal system.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The Bektashi tarika generally followed the legal rulings of the Hanafi madhab, which was the official Ottoman madhab, and one of the four Sunni madhabs practiced within the Ottoman Empire.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: While members of the Ottoman janissary corps generally belonged to the Bektashi tarika, this was an institutionalized military force that existed to serve the Ottoman state, and not the Bektashi

tarika.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:
– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):
– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:
– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Ottoman Turkish was the most common written language under the Ottoman Empire; Arabic was also used.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, the religious calendar was the same for all Muslims, although the exact date of holidays depended on local conditions (in particular, whether the moon could be sighted in that location).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Larger Bektashi tekkes often featured a bakehouse in conjunction with the women's quarters (ekmek evi), as well as general kitchens (ash evi). (Tschudi p. 1162).

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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General References

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